

Government Finance and Housing Delivery of Selected Local Governments in Ogun State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The problem of housing globally became aggravated after the scourge of Covid 19 in 2020. Mainly affected are the increasing low-income earners in developing countries struggling with over population without a corresponding housing supply and stable mortgage programme. This made it imperative to study the phenomenon of housing deficit in Ogun State. The objective of this study is to look at the nexus between housing deficit vis a vis housing delivery and government finance in Sagamu, Ijebu Ode, Ado Odo Ota and Abeokuta south local governments in Ogun State. The study adopted the exploratory research design and descriptive research design, using both primary and secondary data. Using the convergence theory that argues that its the state solely fiduciary duty to solve housing problems, the study discovered that majority of the respondents lived in houses not befitting for humans, this is because successive governments have consistently neglected growth in population in formulating housing policy because this mainly affects the low income earners. The study recommended a template for proper statistical data on birth rate, middle/low income earners, increased budgetary allocation for housing delivery, construction of low-cost houses that are affordable by the lower class. It concluded that there should be sincerity on the part of the state government and this must begin with judicious spending and accountability of the monthly budget on housing delivery which must not only be affordable but also accessible to low income earners in the state.

Keywords: Housing Deficit, Housing Affordability, Housing Finance, Housing Delivery

Introduction

The problem of housing deficit is a global phenomenon that is more pronounced in developing countries. This problem may be slightly low in developed countries, for example it was 12 million in UK as of the end of 2020 (Simon, 2020) and 3.8 million in US (Freddie, 2021). This crisis has manifested more in developing countries where greater part of the population live in informal settlements. In South Africa, more than 1.1 million households are estimated to be living in informal settlements of nine major cities (Agayi and Karakayali, 2020). This condition, according to Agayi and Karakayali (2020), is similar in developing Southern Eastern Europe. In Albania and Macedonia, about

a quarter of the population live in informal settlements occupying about 40% and 11%, respectively. These settlements are without access to affordable and decent housing, water sanitation, electricity among others.

In sub Saharan Africa, according to Aminu (2019), 70% of housing stock are of poor quality and out of compliance with local regulation. However, housing is a basic need of man hence the reason for describing it as a sine-qua-non of human living (Olotuah & Aiyetan, 2006). Consequently, the importance attached to the issue of housing is immense; to most governments, the availability of sufficient but basic housing for all is often stated as a priority for enhancing the social needs of the society. The inability of various governments to meet these social needs has led to the multiplicity of global slums.

A house can be described as a physical structure meant for the provision of shelter to its occupants, it can also be used it to protect persons from harsh effects of weather and other dangerous things that may cause harm to their lives (Aminu, 2019). Thus, housing is one of the basic physiological needs of man, since shelter is always ranked next to food and clothing based on priority needs for every human being. For a typical Nigerian, the house is a major asset in his portfolio, the purchase of a house represents the cogent lifelong investment and a store of wealth (Akinwunmi, 2009). Consequently, the provision of housing services depends on a good functional housing finance system dependent on the economic system adopted in a country (Akinwunmi, 2009).

Nigeria is a West African country that shares land borders with the Republic of Benin in the West, Chad and Cameroon in the East and Niger Republic in the North. The country is bounded in the South by the Atlantic Ocean. With the effect of the Covid 19 pandemic on an already crawling economy, International monetary fund projected a contraction of GDP by 3.1/4 % in 2020, with subdued growth of 1.1/2% within 2021 and 0% by 2022 (IMF, 2020). Consequently, the income earned by Nigerian workers became abysmally low, where the minimum monthly wage is US \$67 (30,000) (rate at US \$1 = 450).

Housing deficit in Nigeria stands between sixteen to twenty-two million up from eight million in the 1980's (Fakoyejo, 2020). It is also estimated that over twenty-two million are either homeless or live in rented substandard houses. For the housing deficit to be abated, more than 59.5 trillion naira is required (Onoji, 2021). Recently, the Minister of Housing, Raji Fashola, refuted his earlier assertion that housing deficit in Nigeria remains the creation of the imagination of the Federal Housing Agency. To him, the earlier mentioned deficit has no scientific or logical basis. He argued that there are many empty houses in the villages, unoccupied (Onoji, 2021). Nevertheless, if the argument by the Honourable Minister of Housing is correct, how then can the housing demand and shortages in urban centres be accounted for?

Generating finance for housing development has become more like an insurmountable barrier making credit financing very inevitable (Ademuliyi, 2010). This is because housing finance plays a major role in determining the quality and tenure of housing consumption, the overall financing portfolio

of the public and the stability and effectiveness of the financial system. A well-functioning mortgage market is considered to have large external benefits to the domiciled national economy like contribution to economic growth and improved standard of living (Renaud 2008; Dickerson 2009). With the absence of a well-functioning housing finance system, a market-based provision would therefore be lacking. In most developing countries, their housing finance supply systems are considered to be operationally efficient in terms of intermediation (Kim 1977; Cho 2007) (cited in Akinwunmi 2009). These efficiencies include reductions in the cost of credit intermediation but this has not been able to close the housing deficit to a minimal level. For example, in 2017, 10.2% of households in European Union (EU) spent over 40% of their disposable income on housing credits, but this share reduces to 37.8% when considering households at risk of poverty. At the same time, when housing costs are taken into account, 156 million people were at risk of poverty, as against 85 million before housing cost are taken into account. Thus, by 2018, the estimated investment gap in affordable housing in EU stands at 57 billion per year (European Union, 2019).

In Africa, despite government intervention at various levels, housing problem continue to generate an increasing number of poor urban residents that have become homeless (Aminu 2019). According to the World Bank report of about 70% represent the urban housing stock in sub-Saharan Africa, 50% in South Asia, 25% in Latin America and the Caribbean. Again, they are of poor quality and out of compliance with local regulations. Medium usable living space in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia is about seven square meters (75 square feet) per person compared to 32 square meters (350 square feet) in the industrial countries. Per capital expenditures on roads, sewage, drainage, water supply, electricity supply and garbage collection is 10-40 times greater in the industrialized countries than the way it is in the developing countries (Aminu, 2019).

Statement of the Problem

The escalating global housing crisis is one of humans' greatest challenges, especially after the Covid 19 pandemic of 2020. At least 1.2 billion people worldwide live in substandard housing, often lacking access to basic services and infrastructure (CBN, 2020). This is increasing rapidly in the context of accelerating urban population growth, especially in rapidly urbanising Africa and Asia (Andrew et.al, 2020). The World Bank projects that 300 million new homes will be required by 2030 to bridge the global housing deficit, with the majority of this need concentrated in sub-Saharan Africa, South Asia and South East Asia. This will require a global investment of 17 trillion dollars to facilitate land acquisition and housing construction. (Andrew etal, 2020). Although, the challenge is vast, the opportunity is also enormous, in the UK, housing deficit was 12 million as the end of 2020 (Simon, 2020) while in the US the deficit is 3.8 million (Freddie, 2021).

In Nigeria, housing deficit continues to grow and according to the Minister of Housing Raji Fashola in 2020, it was estimated to be 22 million. Nigeria's housing backlog continues to pose health

challenge to many individuals as 60 to 79% of Nigerians are slum dwellers (Bah et.al 2018 in CAHF, 2020). This makes them vulnerable to the transmission of communicable disease. According to world health organisation, human to human transmission of the Covid-19 virus largely occurs in families while a secondary transmission rate of Covid-19 is higher in clusters of large households (WHO, 2020). The housing stock in Nigeria is estimated at 10.7million, out of which only about 5% is in formal mortgage (CBN, 2020). The widening gap between housing demand and supply is caused by a multiplicity of factors including land acquisition, high cost of building materials, lack of proper land regulation and policy.

Many government intervention policies and programmes have evolved over time to address the issue with no solution (Anunike, 2011). These include promoting and energising primary mortgage institutions (PMIs) to raise fund and loan for housing projects the reorganisation of Federal Housing Authority (FHA) to focus on social housing, home ownership scheme for civil servants by monetising their benefits and giving them opportunity to purchase government house; reviews of National Urban Development and Housing Policies in 2004 to ensure that all Nigerians should have decent, safe and sanitary housing accommodation at affordable cost. Government white paper on the recommendation the of Presidential Review Committee on Housing in 2008, the annual target of providing a thousand housing units per annum by each state government, Urban Development Bank of Nigeria (UDBN), Federal Housing Authority (FHA) reforms among others. (Abayomi et.al, 2020).

In 2018, the government of Nigeria, in partnership with the World Bank and other developing partners, took significant strides to unlock these housing constraints. They are: (a) conducive macro policies that provide for stable and low inflation (b) access to long term finance (c) reduced cost to business transactions in land registration and foreclosure (d) good quality and efficient building and construction. This outgone World Bank/Nigeria Housing Finance Programme attracted the sum of 300 million dollars between 2018 to 2020 (World Bank, 2018).

Nevertheless, with all these aforementioned strides of Nigerian government, housing deficit has continued to grow unabated, this has led to multi-faceted problems such as: multiplicity of slums, flooding of urban centres, congestion, increased crime rate, traffic jam, transfer of communicable disease among others, over- stretching of public infrastructural facilities and high rent rate.

Thus, in spite of the huge financial resources ploughed into the provision of housing by various administrations and their agencies, housing deficit in Nigeria still persists. This study therefore aims at investigating the reasons financial efforts put into remedying housing deficits in Nigeria may not have yielded substantial dividends and accordingly provides the way forward.

Research Objectives

The main objective of the study is to examine how government finance has affected housing deficit in the selected local governments in Ogun State. The specific objectives of this study, however are to:

- 1 Determine the reasons government lacks the will in considering population growth in the formulation processes of Nigeria's numerous housing policies especially in selected local governments of Ogun State.
- 2 Access the reasons housing shortages is growing unabated despite the governments' yearly budget for housing provision in Ogun States.
- 3 Examine the relationship between housing affordability and level of income in accessing government loans through various mortgages banks.
- 4 Identify the problems associated with housing deficit and government finance in these selected local governments of Ogun State.

Literature Review

Housing: The English word 'house' is derived directly from the old English word 'hus' sourced the from proto German word *husan*, meaning “dwelling, shelter or home” .Housing is one of the three basic needs of man following closely after food, which is the most important factor for the survival of man; it is among the important measures of the state of an economy. Housing is considered to be one of the best indicators of a person's standard of living and place in the society (Jiboye, 2009). The concept transcends just providing a roof over one's head (Akinmoladun & Oduwaje, 2000). It forms the base upon which people could rebuild their lives following the disruptive impacts and trauma of homelessness (Smith et.al, 2014).

A house is a building that functions as a home or an abode that provides adequate shelter for individuals and families (Adenubi & Windapo, 2007). Access to appropriate and accessible housing is a fundamental human right that is vital to the wellbeing of individual, families and committees (Select Committee, 2008). Aribigbola (2008) posits that housing is a basic need of human being just as food and clothing are. It is very fundamental to the welfare, survival and health of man (Fadamiro et.al, 2004). Hence, housing is one of the best indicators of a person's standard of living and his place in the society.

To Aminu (2019), housing can be described as a physical structure meant for the provision of shelter or accommodation for its occupants, to protect them from harsh weather and other dangerous things that might cause harm to their lives. Olawale et.al (2015) corroborated this, that housing is not only a building that comprises all inbuilt amenities that make life comfortable for the inhabitant, but also it embraces all the environment qualities that make a particular unit livable (Zanuzdana et.al, 2012). It is a major economic asset in every nation (Amao & Odujo, 2014).

From the foregoing, the significance of a decent house in modern society cannot be overemphasized, as it is essential to humans not just as a source of protection from external effect, but as a point of basic gathering where important economic, social and political activities are nurtured and pursued (Oladimeji, 2015)

Housing Deficit

The concept of housing deficit may be tricky to define because it is a consequence of the problems associated with housing itself. Nevertheless, housing deficit refers to the number of shelters which do not have the necessary adequacies to be regarded as habitable, plus the number of housing units that need to be built to shelter all families who currently lack one and as a result, share a shelter with one another in overcrowded conditions (Iwedi & Onuegbu, 2014). It has been identified as the concentration of families earning three times less than the minimum wage, caught in the poverty cycle, and with a family income structurally limited and as a result they are unable to afford proper housing (World Bank, 2013).

AOL (2019) conceptualizes housing deficit as a deficiency or lack in the number of houses needed to accommodate the population of an area. It follows the economic principles of supply and demand. When production of housing outpaces the demand, there will be housing surplus, when housing production falls behind demand there is housing deficit or shortage. This can be measured as the difference between the number of households and the number of permanent dwellings. The deficit can be estimated for a given period of time, as annual deficit or can sometimes be referred to as housing backlog (Moore, 2019).

Housing Policy: A policy is a conscious system of principle meant to guide decisions and secure rational objective. It is a statement of intent, generally implemented as a procedure through programmes. To this end, different sections of the economy has policies that are used in tackling peculiar problems. Hence, housing policy is a tool that is used in town planning for solving housing problems, and consequently, for the achievement of sustainable housing (Olawale et.al, 2015).

A housing policy is derived from laws, regulations and administrative practices that can aid the production and delivery of housing. It is a policy measure aimed purposely at solving housing problems and it requires a strategy for the enforcement of the purpose of the intended programmes of actions. A most comprehensive housing policy should address the role of government which may vary from the planning and control of the aspects of housing production: land, investment, construction and occupancy to intervention only at certain levels or when solutions are needed to tackle specific problem involving such matters as land use plans and controls, credit and financial aids. Subsidies should go to low income groups, rent control, slum clearance and relocation (Lawal, 1997).

Housing Affordability

The term housing affordability has come into popular usage in the last four decades replacing housing need at the center of the debate about the provision of adequate housing for all (Ndubueze, 2009). This is because inability of the decision makers to find a balance among analysis for housing demand, housing supply, household income and size distribution as well as the mobility to comprehend what housing

affordability really entails. It is difficult to define affordable housing, and there is no generally acceptable definition (Mekenya, 1996 cited in Oyediran 2019). While low cost refers only to building system and land development methods that are applicable to low cost housing, affordable housing should generate an image of typical housing that may be large or small, built with inexpensive materials and products and provide the amenities appropriate for or lack of affordability is determined by the household income of the occupant rather than the cost of the house (Wallace, 1995 cited in Oyediran, 2019).

Housing affordability can be defined as the capacity of making households meet their periodic mortgage needs without jeopardizing their health or reducing other basic family need (Agbola, 2005 cited in John et.al, 2015). Housing is considered affordable if it consumes 30% or less of a household's income (Community Tool Box, 2018). The choice of an affordable house goes beyond having a roof over one's head; it involves choosing your neighbourhood, amenities and the services that come with it (Wilson, 2018). The ability to access wealth by the majority of the citizens often puts upward pressure and competition from high-income and the masses on housing prices, thereby putting a high risk for low income mass (Community Tool Box, 2018). Put differently, it is the ability to afford housing (Ndubueze, 2009).

The concept of affordable housing has been measured by the income level, household size and affordability (KPMG, 2010). Affordable housing has been used to mean “public or social” or 'low cost' housing. For the purpose of housing affordability, Palade and Khare (2015) categorized the citizens according to their income levels. Four categories are identified, they are: Economically Weaker Group (EWG), Lower Income Group (LIG), Middle Income Group (MIG), and the High-Income Group (HIG). The major demand in housing is from the EWG, LIG and MIG categories. A general yardstick for affordable housing is that expenditure on housing should not exceed 30% of the income of the household. As expected, the 30% of household income benchmark has been a subject of debate among experts. Hulchanski (2005) raised the issue of shelter poverty, a situation where a household spends 30% of their income on housing but could not afford to meet some other essential needs for minimal comfortable living. This scenario arises, where though the cost of housing is low, the income is also so low that the household cannot afford non-housing needs after spending 30% of its income on housing.

Housing Finance: Housing, as a social and economic product, has a positive impact on the economy of any country. Developed countries such as the UK, some part of North America, Germany, Japan, Singapore among others, have a well-organized and effective housing finance system (Okoroafor, 2007 cited in Wapara et.al 2011). In Nigeria, housing finance systems are generally underdeveloped despite having good policies, but affected by poor methods of implementation which have often led to loss of funds by the government.

The sources of housing finance can be broadly classified into formal and informal. Formal housing finance supply in emerging economies are operated through both the policy driven and the

market-oriented housing finance channels (Deng & Fei, 2008 in Akinwunmi, 2009). The policy driven housing finance supply is mainly through housing funds schemes which are mandatory housing savings scheme while the market-oriented housing finance supply is mainly commercial loans from financial institution.

For the acquisition or building of a house, the most popular means of raising finance in Nigeria has either been from institutions, which are universal banks, mortgage institution, insurance companies and state housing corporation or from the informal financial market. The provision of finance and facilities especially for lower middle-class groups for construction are provided through the informal sector (Wapare et.al, 2011). The type of finance being raised from the financial institution is called 'debt financing' and it represent a small percentage the of total housing finance lending figure with the financial system. This is because over 50% of potential borrowers earn low income and cannot meet the condition attached to borrowing for housing finance by the lenders.

Housing Problems in Nigeria

The problem of housing in Nigeria in terms of stock and quality have remained persistent. Many government intervention policies and programmes have evolved over time to address the issues. With a household remuneration of 39 million, over 17 million housing deficits in Nigeria (World Bank, 2016) are colossal, realistically overwhelming and worryingly on an increase. Nigeria's population is increasing at about 2.8% annually and the United Nations has projected that by 2050, the population in Nigeria would be about 400 million.

Figure 1: Nigeria Population Projection (1950-2100)

Source: UN Population Review (2019)

Migration has contributed significantly to the growth rate of the urban population estimated to be 4.7% by the World bank. Expectedly, the high urban population growth rate will lead to rapid deterioration in housing and living conditions (Oyediran, 2019). The World Bank (2015), reported that sub-Saharan Africa, including Nigeria experiencing rapid urbanization, as well as, a growing slum population. The

report further observed that many households cannot afford basic formal housing or access mortgage loans.

World Bank (2015) noted that there is a lack of quality housing stock, and that the consistent and reliable data to identify the quantity and quality of housing deficit both formal and informal is quite challenging. Various interest groups escalated the figure of population and statistical magnitude so as to sound the alarm and draw attention to the need for the housing sector. It has been reported that housing deficit in Nigeria stands at about 17million (Adebayo & Dada 2014; Abuja Housing Forum, 2019, Okonjo-Iweala 2014; Alegbe, 2013; Centre for Affordable Housing Finance in Africa, (2013) with attendant financial requirement to bridge the gap estimated to be about #60 trillion. On the other hand, Garba et.al (2017) believed that the Nigerian housing deficit is between 17 to 20 million housing units. Akinradewo and Adedokun (2019) reported recently that the Managing Director of the Federal Mortgage Bank of Nigeria (FMBN) estimated that the deficit in Nigeria is about 22 million units. The confusion in the unavailability and unreliability of these estimates compounded the problem of housing in Nigeria.

Scholars have offered a wide array of reasons for the problem of housing deficits in Nigeria. Ezeigwe (2015) averred that the indicators of urban housing deficit in Nigeria are poverty, urbanization, high cost of land, non-implementation of the housing policies, failure on the side of the government, high cost of building materials and corruption. Ibimilua and Ibitoye (2015), averred that housing problem is militated against by poverty, discrimination against the use of local materials, ineffective housing finance, inadequate financial instrument for the mobilization of funds, high cost of building materials, shortage of infrastructural facilities, as well as the bureaucracies in land acquisition, processing of Certificate of Occupancy(C of O) and approval of building plans. Olarenwaju et.al (2016) argued that ineffective policies and regulations, legal issues, ineffective market regulations and high costs of construction are the reasons for the deficit. Ewurum and Odenigbe (2018) blamed ineffective demographic management and affordability, defining demography management as the integration of population statistics in decision making. The affordability angle also finds support in the works of Ahmed and Bin Span (2019). Again, Okafor (2016) and Ifediora et.al (2015) posit that low-income earners are the predominant demography of housing deficit in Nigeria. Okafor (2016) extrapolated that housing deficit in Nigeria emanates from an agglomeration of lack or inadequate housing financial assistance, high cost of building materials, high interest rates and lukewarm interest on the part of the financial institution to facilitate loans to real estate developments. He further queried: Where then are the government public private partnership cooperative housing development loans, national housing mortgage fund and rent to own schemes implemented?

Ahmed and Bin-Span (2019) supported and posited that public housing delivery in Nigeria is characterized by lack of proper framework which included, land accessibility and affordability, corruption, lack of sound legal framework, funding constraints and unstable price of building

materials”. Ifediora et.al (2015), held that these characteristics were consequential upon “little or no market research, poor direction, poor project locations, stringent affordability criteria and corruption and lack of trust by the masses. In support, Gbadegesin et.al (2016) suggested tenure security and land availability as major causes of housing deficit in Nigeria. This contribution brings the Nigerian Land Use Act (1978) into disrepute, since the Land Use Act was enacted to make land available for development through government control of tenure and use. Why then is land not available for development? Ezeigwe (2015) attempted a response with the avowal that the process is littered and laced with corruption which transmutes the policy from societal welfare to promoting benefit.

To Temi et.al (2018), problems of housing deficit are multi-faceted they include: high cost and lack of equal access to land, high cost of building materials, high cost and long processing direction of proper registration; inability of earlier policies and programs to adequately resolve the backlog of housing problems, absence of proper and evaluation of public housing policies and programs, low capacity of public housing agencies, poor government administration, inadequate funding, insufficient infrastructural amenities, as well as inadequate housing finance. Iwedu & Onuelugbu (2014), supported by itemizing the problem of housing deficit in Nigeria under the following: outdated mortgage laws, paucity of funds, rapid urbanization and economic growth, poor mortgage system, corruption in high quarters, poor state of infrastructure, poor policy implementation and steady population growth. Similarly, Isa et.al (2013) posited by looking at the economic angle. They affirm the housing sector as having a multiplier effect, and in most developed economies, the housing sector is seen as an important sector for stimulating economic growth.

Appraising the literatures above, the following can be deduced: First, low income earners make up the bulk of housing deficit demography in Nigeria. Secondly, Nigeria produces a deficit remuneration of 600,000 housing units annually and this implies that with an annual population growth rate of almost 3%, instead of reducing the deficit, it seems that Nigeria is subconsciously increasing the deficit. Thirdly, public housing supply has benefitted mostly the middle to high income demography if not predominantly the high. Fourthly, attempts by public housing providers in Nigeria to curb the deficit have been misconstrued, misdirected and have not prioritized the demands of the predominant demography. Delmendo (2019), concurred with the assertion that in Lagos Nigeria, over 70% of the population live in informal settlement and slums, a situation that is rife all over Nigeria.

Government Efforts on Housing Delivery in Ogun State

Ogun State inherited the Western region policy of encouraging house ownership by its workforce rather than depending on the provision of houses by the government. As at 1976, therefore, there were only two estates in the state; one in Abeokuta and one in Ijebu-ode. The provision of housing in Ogun State by the Federal Government Housing Agency (FHA) includes the 1975-1980 Development Plan period when the Federal Housing Authority (FHA) allocated 893 plots and completed 512 housing out of the

8000 housing plus land projected for the state. The emergent creation of State Housing Corporation in 1997: an offshoot of the Western Nigeria housing corporation gave birth to 200 and 350 housing units respectively at Oke-Afa and Ijebu Ode (Omole, 2001). The state also participated in the federal government housing program (1976-1980), where all the twenty states of the federation were mandated to build 4000 housing unit each (Nwaka, 2005).

Source: Compiled by the Researcher 2021

The above figure shows the billions of naira invested in housing delivery in Ogun state in the last five years. With an estimate of over 500,000 housing deficits in 2020 and predominantly low and middle income earners, housing demand remains a problem in the state.

Ogun State Housing Corporation (OSHC) is the oldest state government owned public housing agency. It came into existence through the enactment of the Ogun State Edict No 11 1977 and was closely followed by the creation of Ogun State Property and Investment Corporation established by Edict No-10 of 1985; these are the major agencies in charge of housing production and delivery in Ogun State. In 2003, the Ministry of Housing was carved out of the old Ministry of Works and Housing and a year later the Gateway Saving and Loans were established.

Theoretical Framework

The Convergence Theory

This was propounded by Prof. Berkey Clark in the 1960s. The theory has its roots in fundamentalist perspective economics but has later been applied to other fields by various researchers. Convergence theory is based on the role of the state in housing sector, especially on how the socially oriented policies became necessary as societies entered into the post industrialization phase of development. When

applied to housing, the convergence theory argues that the state should work to solve housing problems, given the economic and demographic changes that might occur during the country's development; changes like industrialization and urbanization where housing was originally left to the private sector (the employers). This unregulated system left many in low quality housing and in an expensive tenure system (Dewide & De Decker, 2016). This resulted in a societal change where people desired that housing provision became a necessary part of a modern welfare state (Donnison & Ungerson, 1982; Vander Heijden, 2013 in CEB, 2017). In the post-World War II era, the role of the state heightened as societies throughout the continent coalesced to tackle collective issues. One of which was to provide adequate housing after years of which that had left the continent with severe housing shortages.

Doling (1990) criticized the convergence theory, saying that housing market and housing policies cannot be explained by reference to convergence theory. That is, they are not the direct product of the economic and demographic industrialization, but are primarily determined by ideological and institutional factor.

Methodology

The study adopted both exploratory and descriptive research design, a mixed system of data collection using both secondary and primary data. Content analysis, descriptive statistics and quantitative statistical tool were also employed as data analysis methods. In this research, four research questions were raised and four hypotheses drawn in an effort to answer these questions. The population of this study consist of the local government staff of Sagamu, Ijebu Ode, Ado Odo Ota, Abeokuta South and selected community development association. A sample of 363 copies of questionnaire administered was drawn out of a population of 3921. Using systematic sampling method 363 questionnaires was administered but 336 questionnaires was returned. Data analysis was carried out using inferential statistics.

Data Analysis

Summary of Results

HYPOTHESES	RESULTS	DECISIONS
The failure of various Nigerian housing policies to be proactive about population growth has led to the decrease of slums and infrastructural decay among these selected local governments' in Ogun States.	$R = 0.379, R^2 = 0.144, F_{(1,335)} = 56.161, \beta_{FVNHP} = 0.597$ and $p < 0.05$ Null hypothesis is not accepted	The failure of various Nigerian housing policies to be proactive about population growth has led to the increase of slums and infrastructural decay among the selected local governments in Ogun States.
Governments' yearly budget on public housing delivery has drastically reduced housing shortages among the selected local governments in Ogun State.	$R^2 = 0.165, F_{(1,335)} = 66.085, \beta_{BUDGET} = 0.246$ and $p < 0.05$ Null hypothesis is not accepted	Governments' yearly budget on public housing delivery has not drastically reduced housing shortages among the selected local governments in Ogun State.
There is no relationship between housing affordability and level of income in Ogun State.	$r = 0.180, p < 0.05$. Null hypothesis is not accepted	There is a significantly low positive relationship between housing affordability and level of income in Ogun State.
The problem of housing deficit and government finance do not directly affect housing availability in Ogun state	$R^2 = 0.138, F_{(1,335)} = 53.261, \beta_{PHFD} = 0.349$, and $p < 0.05$ Null hypothesis is not accepted	The problem of housing deficit and government finance directly affect housing availability in Ogun State.

Source: Researcher's Result (October 2021)

Interpretation

From the table above, hypothesis one of the study was tested to achieve the first objective, using two indicators which are failure of housing policies, multiplication of slums and infrastructural decay. It was discovered that the government has consciously neglected growth in population and this has led to multiplication of slums and infrastructural decay in the state. The table also showed that hypothesis two was tested to achieve the second objective, using the indicators of accessibility of housing schemes by low/middle income earners and availability of soft loans, the study discovered the respondent had little

or no access to these indicators. Hypothesis three was tested to achieve the third objective, using the indicators of level of income and accessibility to government housing loans. The study discovered that the level of income is a determinant in housing affordability cum majority of the respondent do not have access to any Ogun State housing loans. Finally, hypothesis four from the table was tested to achieve the fourth objective, using the indicators: reasons for the failure of housing policies, problems associated with housing deficit and government finance, the study discovered that problems such as security of land, citing of housing scheme, lack of affordability, poor habitability and inadequate planning are the major causes of the problems of housing policy failure, housing deficit and government finance in Ogun state.

Summary and Conclusion

The failure of various housing policies in Nigeria to address the victims of housing deficit has led to disconnection between the government and the governed in many Nigerian states. This is because one of the essence of governance is to enact social policies that ensure citizens reside in houses befitting of a man as enshrined in the UN-Habitat Agreement of 2006. First and mostly mentioned by the respondents is the level of insincerity on the part of the government as policy makers. Several reasons attributed to these are: Majority of the housing policies are meant for the rich because government has consciously failed to consider the ever-growing population of the lower class, lack of statistical data for low/middle income earners in order to determine the accurate number of housing deficit.

Secondly, housing shortages have continued to grow unabated because of the neglect of the growth in population during the process of housing policy formulation. This in turn has led to implementation of faulty, lopsided and unrealistic policies which engendered the multiplication of slums as well as infrastructural decay in Ogun State. This appears to be the norm because the public infrastructure that was provided for few citizens is now overstretched by a larger population resulting in infrastructural decay plus overt increase in cost of maintenance.

Thirdly, it was discovered that majority of the low/middle income earners cannot afford the few government housings schemes. For example, the new Federal Government National Housing Programme in 34 states, perfected a one-bedroom apartment to be sold for #7.2 million with a down payment of #2.16million, how little under, a low/middle income earner with #30,000 minimum wage could afford this? Finally, the study concludes and exposed the limiting factors against poor government finance leading to housing deficit, chief among which are unreliable statistical data and lack of political will.

The findings and conclusion of this study is in line with the previous studies such as Oyediran (2019), Aminu (2019), Abayomi et al. (2020), Agayi & Karakayachi (2020), Ewurun et al(2020), Odunjo (2014), Patrick (2016), Iwedi & Ouegbu (2014), Aluko (2010), Adegun et al (2009).

Recommendations

One recommendation that flows from this study is the need to revisit the subsisting housing policies of the states under study and make the same cost friendly, especially to the capacities of the low/middle income class. Also, it recommends the need for accurate statistics that captures the rate of birth in the states, number of income earners and rate of housing deficit. The government of Ogun states need to come up with a template that captures above mentioned for appropriate planning. The study recommends that the government of Ogun State should give priority to the housing sector by increasing the yearly budgetary allocation and ensure proper accountability by public officers in charge of housing delivery.

Again, the study recommends that, government should be sincere with housing schemes especially as regards affordability for the low/middle income earners. This may be achievable through the delivery of that will not require huge initial deposits or through a build and allocate arrangement that will require only a monthly payback programme.

Additionally, the study also recommends that government of Ogun State should make the mortgage market viable and conscientize the general public about their need to patronise mortgage houses. In most developed countries, a viable mortgage market is one among the major drivers of economic growth. In the words of Renaud (2008) and Dickerson (2009), they argued that a well-functioning mortgage market is considered to have a large external benefit to domiciled national economy like contribution to economic growth and improved standard of living. A viable mortgage market will also create job opportunities. Again, equally the populace should be conscientize about the benefit of patronizing mortgage banks has it far outweighs just accessing of housing loans.

Finally, the study recommends that there must be political will by the government. This is imperative because the support of the political leadership of any economy is very germane to the survival of any public policy. As such, the governments Ogun State must show the willingness to pursue their housing policies to logical conclusion especially through implementation, since, if policies are not successfully implemented the well fondness of such policy is a mere effort in vain.

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